

FATIGUE OF HIGHLY DAMPED CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTIC PANELS AT HIGH TEMPERATURE

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ABSTRACT

There is considerable interest in the use of composite materials in aerospace structures. One important area is to develop a stiff, lightweight composite material with a highly damped, high temperature polymer matrix material. This study concerns the application of such material in the form used in thin skin panels of aircraft and investigation of its fatigue properties at room and high temperature. Flexural fatigue tests have been carried out at two different temperatures and harmonic three-dimensional FE analyses were performed in order to understand the dynamic behaviour of plates. Parameter studies were also performed in order to examine various methods for including damping in the structure, and conclusions have been drawn concerning optimal incorporation of a highly damped matrix material into a high performance structure.

INTRODUCTION

Significant areas of primary and secondary structure in military aircraft are close to jet effluxes. These parts of the aircraft usually operate at high temperature and high levels of random acoustic loading. The need for a carbon fibre reinforced plastic material with a high temperature polymer matrix and high fatigue resistance is pressing. Highly damped composite structures should be developed in order to have an enhanced fatigue life in order to better resist dynamic loading.

Work has previously been carried out on improving the damping in fibre reinforced plastic (FRP) composites by White [1], Abdin [2], Willway [3], and Drew [4]. Results given have mainly been for FRP studies at relatively low temperatures. Conclusions were then made regarding the resin matrix, the effects of shear, the use of short fibres and the manufacture of highly damped CFRP structures. A number of approaches can be taken to improve the damping properties of polymeric composites, such as:

- 1—Maximisation of damping through the development of more highly dissipative resins.

2—Investigation into the use of mixed fibre reinforcements, including fibres which dissipate more energy.

3—Optimisation of frictional interface damping such as through use of fibre coatings and surface treatments.

4—Development of resins with wider glass transition regions.

5—Incorporation of several resins within a composite, each resin having a different transition temperature. In this way, a composite could be produced which has high overall damping through a wide temperature range.

A range of prepregs, i.e.: T800/6376, T800/5245, Kevlar/913, T800/924, T400/6376, Glass/913, IM6/6376 and XAS/913 were used in test specimens to investigate damping characteristics and results were promising. The range of glass transition temperature (T_g) lay between 140°C and 230°C and the loss factors were high ranging between 0.15 and 0.275. The MY720 resin was also tested, either on its own or with various proportions of DGA included and results were such that T_g varied from from 206°C to 277°C.

The work reported upon here forms part of a current project within which lightweight composite materials with highly damped, high temperature polymer matrix material are being studied, by investigating its fatigue characteristics and dynamic properties.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

A preliminary investigation was made in order to find the most adequate, existing high temperature resins. Two different prepregs were highlighted: LaRC RP46 and SE300. The LaRC RP46 material, which has a glass transition temperature of 349°C, was developed by members of the NASA Langley Research Center. The LaRC RP46 material acquired was 0.125 mm thick unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced prepreg and had 60% fibre volume fraction. SE300 developed by SP systems is very promising since it has a glass transition temperature of 300°C with an outstanding thermo-oxidative stability, a good adhesion to aluminium, excellent surface characteristics and a standard epoxy processing technique. Material properties of the LaRC RP46 material were provided by the manufacturer while no data were available for the SE300 material. The SE300 material acquired was carbon fibre reinforced prepreg of (0°/90°) woven form, 0.25 mm thick. Five specimens of about 20 mm long and 12 mm wide were manufactured in order to carry DMTA analyses. Their stacking sequences were as follows: (0°/90°)₄, (0°/90°)₈, (+45°/-45°)₄, (-45°/+45°)₄, (0°/90°, 45°/45°)₈ and (45°/45°, 0°/90°)₈. Results from a DMTA test are shown in Fig. 1 for a SE300 specimen with (+45°/-45°)₄ lay-up. The logarithm of the storage modulus as well as the loss factor are plotted. The loss factor values vary from 0.0097 to 0.085 for a range of temperature from 45°C to 300°C. Table 1 shows the loss factor and the Young's modulus values at 40°C and T_g .

The fatigue behaviour of the materials in flexure had to be studied and compared to that of material already in use; i.e. with known fatigue data. LaRC RP46 and SE300 specimens, 140 mm long, 70 mm wide and 1mm thick, were made with the following stacking sequences: (\pm 45°/0°/90°)₈ and (45°/45°, 0°/90°)₈ respectively. Unfortunately, voids and delaminations existed in all LaRC RP46 specimens and it was found out later that it apparently has a rather poor processability. Flexural fatigue tests were then carried out with SE300 samples. The flexural fatigue rig used is described in detail in Benchechou [5]. The apparatus consists of a 16 mm diameter, motor driven shaft, on which is mounted a "roller" grip consisting of two rollers which are positioned above and below the specimen and set so as to exert a slight "pinch" on the specimen surfaces at one end, the other end being clamped. The rig has been designed in such a way that the rollers follow the displacement and rotational movement of the plate without

inducing bending at the end of the specimen. Sine clamps, as designed by Drew [6] were used at the clamped end of the specimen so that no edge peeling would occur while samples were being tested; damage instead is induced in the centre of the specimen. The aim of the mechanical fatigue test was to cyclically load specimens in order to determine how many cycles would be needed for damage to occur, and its subsequent growth rate. Fatigue tests of two specimens S3 and S4, at a level of $8000\mu\text{S}$, located by the peak of the half-sine clamp, were carried out at room temperature and 210°C respectively. The heating system used to raise the temperature of the system consisted of two air blowers positioned at 40 mm above and below the specimen. The air blowers were electronically regulated hot-air guns. The positions of the guns and the temperature of the hot-air were such that the specimen tested had a uniform temperature of $210 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$. Specimens S3 and S4 were mechanically tested and ultrasonic scans were made before any loading cycles and after 100, 500, 1000, 2000, 5000, 10 000 and 20 000 loading cycles. Fig.2a-h and 3a-h show these scans. A small delamination, indicated by lighter areas in the scans, starts to show in both specimens S3 and S4 after 500 loading cycles and increases substantially after 5000 loading cycles. After 5000 loading cycles, the damage area increased more for specimen S4 than specimen S3, which shows that the latter was slightly more fatigue resistant. In other words, when increasing the temperature from 25°C to 210°C , the resistance to fatigue slightly decreased. Specimens made of the XAS/914 material have been mechanically subjected to flexural tests, as presented in [6]. Thus, comparison between the two materials, i.e. SE300 and XAS/914 can be made. Damage propagation occurring in an XAS/914 sample (X1), with a $(0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ stacking sequence, tested at $8000 \mu\text{S}$ level is shown in Figs.4a-h. Note that substantial damage occurs after 1000 loading cycles in specimen X1. This shows that in the limited series of tests carried out here the SE300 specimens presented a better fatigue behaviour than the XAS/914 samples, particularly at room temperature.

ANALYTICAL WORK

The finite element FE method has been chosen to carry out parametric studies in order to examine various methods for including damping in a structure. ANSYS software has been used and run in a Silicon Graphics Indy workstation. Theoretical models have been built in order to carry out modal and harmonic analyses of multilayered composite plates (410mm, 280mm, 2mm). The plates were fully clamped along all edges. A modal analysis was first done in order to determine the natural frequencies. Then, the plate was driven by harmonic loading at one point of application. The forcing frequency varied from 0 to 400Hz. The amplitude of the load was 50 N. Results for displacements and response phase angles relative to the force for a chosen position on the plate as a function of frequency were obtained. The idea was then to carry out parameter studies in order to examine various methods for including damping in the structure, i.e. to use highly damped matrix material throughout the whole structure or possible incorporation in a few layers.

SIMULATIONS WITH LARC RP46

Models were built up with the following stacking sequence $(\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$. Modal analyses showed that the first three modal frequencies of the panel were as follows:

- 1-105.40Hz
- 2-311.13Hz
- 3-378.45Hz

In order to carry out parameter studies, material damping was included. This allowed models to be run with a different damping value, β_i , in each ply of the panel. The structural damping depends on the natural frequency:

$$\beta_i = 2 \xi / \omega_i \quad (1)$$

$$= \xi / (\pi f_i) \quad (2)$$

where:

$$\omega_i = 2\pi f_i, \quad (3)$$

f_i = the frequency of mode i , Hz

and

ξ =the viscous damping ratio

Analyses were performed considering structural damping for the first and second modes. The material damping was then varied for plies with the same orientation for $\xi = 0.01, 0.02, 0.05, 0.10$ and 0.20 .

Fig. 5 shows the response of the plate at one position, for the first mode and a viscous damping value of 20% in the +45° orientation plies. The damping value was varied through the layers and the response amplitude depends on the level of damping included. From these results, the overall viscous damping ratio of the first mode was calculated for each case in order to see which of the plies contributed the most to heavily damp the plate. Table 2 gives the modal damping value for ANSYS simulation, with $\xi=0.05$ and 0.20 . It is clear that increasing the material damping value of the +45° orientation plies most significantly increased the overall damping value of the panel. In fact, putting a damping value of 20% in the +45° orientation plies lead to a modal damping ratio of 10.36%, which was greater than that achieved with a 10% damping value in all the plies of the structure. Putting a damping value of 20% in the -45° orientation plies lead only to a modal viscous damping ratio of 6.63% while if considering the 0° or 90° orientation plies, the overall viscous damping decreased to 3.80% and 2.57% respectively.

Simulations were also run considering the structural damping of the second mode.

SIMULATION WITH SE300

Models were built up with the following stacking sequence $((45^\circ/45^\circ),(0^\circ/90^\circ))_s$, which was that used for the experimental panels. Modal analyses showed that the first three modal frequencies of the panel were as follows:

1-49.02Hz

2-155.80Hz

3-212.04Hz

Once again, simulations were performed considering the structural damping of the first two modes. Fig. 6 gives the displacement amplitude response at two different points on the panel, varying the structural damping within the (45°/45°) orientation plies (i.e. 20% of viscous damping value), for the first mode. The modal damping ratio was calculated for each simulation and results are given in Table3 for $\xi=0.05, 0.10$ and 0.20 . As can be seen, if high overall damping is needed for a structure with the SE300 material, increasing the damping value of the (45°/45°) orientation plies does most significantly increase the overall damping value of the panel. In fact, putting a damping value of 20% in the (45°/45°) orientation plies lead to an modal viscous damping value of 14.52%, which is better than that achieved with a 10% damping value in all the plies of the structure.

FE ANALYSES AT HIGH TEMPERATURE

Harmonic analyses were carried out with the values of material properties taken at several temperatures. Hence, for the LaRC RP46 models, simulations were carried out with material property values at 260°C and 316°C, while for models with SE300, simulations were performed with material properties at 242°C and 300°C. For LaRC RP46 models, the first mode viscous

damping ratios, when putting a viscous damping value of 20% in the (+45°) orientation plies were 10.44% and 10.67% at 260°C and 316°C respectively. This shows that this material is more highly damped at high temperature. When considering the SE300 models, the modal viscous damping ratios were 1.20%, 1.40% and 1.32% at 25°C, 242°C and 300°C respectively. Models with a damping value of 20% in the (45°/45°) orientation plies lead to modal damping ratios of 14.62% and 14.55% at 242°C and 300°C respectively. This material presents better damping properties of the two materials simulated at 242°C.

CONCLUSIONS

Two matrix materials, SE300 and LaRC RP46, showing promise for use in aircraft structures in a severe environment, i.e. temperature up to 300°C were selected for this study. DMTA analyses have been carried out in order to determine the material properties and results show that these materials have high damping abilities at high temperature. Dynamic loading tests, performed in flexure at room and high temperature showed that the carbon fibre reinforced SE300 material is more fatigue resistant than XAS/914 composite. Modal and harmonic FE analyses permitted determination of the natural frequencies, the dynamic displacements and response phase angles as a function of frequency under the action of point harmonic loading. Conclusions, via parameter studies including material damping, are drawn concerning optimal incorporation of a highly damped matrix material into a high performance structure.

REFERENCES

1. R.G. White., Some measurements of the dynamic properties of mixed, carbon fibre reinforced, plastic beams and plates. *Aeronautical Journal of the Royal Aeronautical Society*, **79**, 318–325 (1975).
2. R.G. White. and E.M.Y. Abdin., Dynamic properties of aligned shortcarbon fibre reinforced plastics in flexure and torsion. *Composites*, 293–306 (1985).
3. T. Willway. and R.G. White., The effects of matrix complex moduli on the dynamic properties of CFRP laminae. *Composites, Science and Technology*, **36**, 77–94 (1989).
4. R.C. Drew., The improvement in damping properties of CFRP materials over a wide temperature range. Unpublished work of the ISVR.
5. B. Benchechou., Stresses around fasteners in composite aircraft structures and effects on fatigue life. PhD Thesis, University of Southampton (1994).
6. R. C. Drew., An investigation into damage initiation and propagation in carbon fibre reinforced plastics. PhD Thesis, University of Southampton (1988).

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Table 1. Loss factor and Young's modulus values at 40°C and at Tg for SE300 samples analysed using the DMTA.

Lay-up	(+45°/-45°) ₄	(+45°/-45°) ₄	(45/45;0/90) ₄	(0°/90°) ₄
Tg (°C)	242.0	242.0	240.3	238.7
η at Tg	0.085	0.085	0.081	0.061
η at 40°C	0.012	0.014	0.010	0.0097
Log E' at 40°C	9.87	9.84	9.97	10.097

Table 2. Overall viscous damping values of LaRC RP46 panels. Values are calculated from results obtained from harmonic analyses; the material damping being considered for the first mode.

Simulation with damping of	+45°orientation plies	-45°orientation plies	0°orientation plies	90°orientation plies
5%	2.92%	2.04%	1.61%	1.31%
20%	10.36%	6.63%	3.80%	2.57%

Table 3. Overall viscous damping values of SE300 panels. Values are calculated from results obtained from harmonic analyses; the material damping being considered for the first mode.

Simulation with damping of	(45°/45°)orientation plies	(0°/90°)orientation plies
5%	3.81%	2.51%
10%	7.06%	3.92%
20%	14.52%	11.57%

Figure 1. Temperature dependence of storage modulus (E') and tan delta (loss factor) for SE300 specimen with (+45°/-45°)₄ lay-up, determined by DMTA technique.

Figure 2. Ultrasonic scans of specimen S3 after applying different numbers of loading cycles. (SE 300 material, ambient temperature)

Figure 3. Ultrasonic scans of specimen S4 after applying different numbers of loading cycles. (SE300 material, 210°C)

a: before any loading cycles b: after 100 loading cycles c: after 500 loading cycles d: after 1000 loading cycles

e: after 2000 loading cycles f: after 5000 loading cycles g: after 10000 loading cycles h: after 20000 loading cycles

Figure 4. Ultrasonic scans of an XAS/914 specimen fatigued at a level of 8000 μ S showing the damage propagation; the lay-up is (0/+45/90)_{2s}, [6].

Figure 5. Response of the LaRC RP46 panel to the harmonic analyses, with a 20% viscous damping ratio in the +45° orientation plies.

Figure 6. Response of the SE300 panel to the harmonic analyses, with a 20% viscous damping ratio in the (45/45) orientation plies.